

Ultrasonic velocity and molecular interaction study of biphenol derivatives at 30 °C

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Abstract : The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and sound velocity (U) (2 MHz) of pure solvents : 1,4-dioxane, methyl ethyl ketone (MEK) and *N,N*-dimethyl formamide (DMF) and solutions of 4,4'-biphenyl diacetate (BPDA) and 4,4'-dihydroxy-3,3'-diethanone biphenyl (DHDEBP) were determined at 30 °C. Various acoustical parameters namely specific acoustical impedance (Z), isentropic compressibility (κ_s), Van der Waals constant (b), intermolecular free path length (L_f), internal pressure (π), free volume (V_f) and solvation number (S_n) were derived from ρ and U data and correlated with concentration (C). A fairly good to excellent correlation is observed between a specified parameter and C . Linear increase of U , Z , b and V_f and linear decrease of κ_s , L_f and π confirmed presence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions. Both BPDA and DHDEBP possess structure forming tendency as confirmed by positive values of S_n . Powerful solute-solute interaction is observed above 0.75 mol/L.

Keywords : Ultrasonic velocity, acoustical parameters, solvation number, molecular interactions.

Introduction

Ultrasonic study is useful in extensive research especially for investigating various organic liquids, liquid mixtures, polymers, etc¹. Ultrasonic study in aqueous and non-aqueous electrolytic solutions furnishes nature and strength of ion-solvent interactions, nature and strength of interactions². It is very important in understanding molecular interactions in binary mixtures³⁻⁶. To our knowledge no work has been reported on ultrasonic study of bisphenol derivatives (1). In present work an effort has been made to explain molecular interactions in three different solvents on the basis of acoustical parameters at 30 °C.

BPDA

DHDEBP

1

Experimental

Solvents used in the present study were purified prior to their use⁷. 4,4'-Dihydroxy biphenol (DHBP) was used as received. 4,4'-Biphenyl diacetate (BPDA) was synthesized by reacting 0.01 mole DHBP with 0.02 mole acetic anhydride at 30 °C. 4,4'-Dihydroxy-3,3'-diethanone biphenyl (DHDEBP) was prepared by Fries rearrangement of BPDA using anhydrous aluminum chloride. Both BPDA and DHDEBP were crystallized three times from methanol-water system. The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) of pure solvents dimethyl formamide (DMF), 1,4-dioxane (DO) and methyl ethyl ketone (MEK) and solutions of BPDA and DHDEBP measurements were carried out at 30 °C using specific gravity bottle, Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer and Mittal Enterprise Interferometer (New Delhi, Model No. F-81) operating at 2 MHz, respectively. The ρ , η and U data were accurate to ± 0.0001 g cm⁻³, ± 0.01 m.Pas and $\pm 0.12\%$, respectively.

Results and discussion

Experimental data on ρ , η and U of pure solvents and solutions at 30 °C are reported in Table 1. Various acoustical parameters (Table 2) such as specific

Table 1. Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) data of BPDA and DHDEBP solutions at 30 °C

Conc. (mol/L)	BPDA			DHDEBP		
	DMF	MEK	DO	DMF	MEK	DO
	ρ (kg/m ³)					
0.00	928.4	773.5	1008.0	928.4	1008.0	773.5
0.25	934.8	776.1	1008.4	935.8	1013.7	776.1
0.50	935.9	782.8	1009.7	936.8	1014.6	782.9
0.75	937.1	793.6	1010.7	937.9	1015.2	784.2
1.00	937.5	802.0	1012.3	938.9	1016.2	785.8
	η (m.Pas)					
0.00	0.753	0.373	0.985	0.753	0.985	0.373
0.25	0.712	0.387	1.102	0.788	1.130	0.366
0.50	0.719	0.399	1.123	0.810	1.166	0.379
0.75	0.724	0.408	1.147	0.820	1.172	0.384
1.00	0.751	0.421	1.162	0.827	1.185	0.394
	U (m s ⁻¹)					
0.00	1465.6	1258.4	1346.8	1465.6	1346.8	1258.4
0.25	1469.6	1267.2	1402.8	1473.6	1347.6	1262.0
0.50	1472.8	1272.8	1510.8	1486.0	1348.4	1264.0
0.75	1477.6	1276.4	1561.2	1498.0	1358.4	1268.0
1.00	1481.2	1280.0	1606.8	1504.4	1360.4	1274.0

Fig. 1. Solvation number S_n against C plots for BPDA and DHDEBP at 30 °C in different solvents.

Table 2. Various acoustical parameters of BPDA and DHDEBP derived from density and ultrasonic velocity data

Conc. (mol/L)	BPDA			DHDEBP		
	DMF	MEK	DO	DMF	MEK	DO
	$Z \times 10^{-5} \text{ (kg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$					
0.00	1.361	0.973	1.358	1.361	0.973	1.358
0.25	1.374	0.983	1.415	1.379	0.979	1.366
0.50	1.378	0.996	1.525	1.392	0.990	1.368
0.75	1.385	1.013	1.578	1.405	0.994	1.379
1.00	1.389	1.027	1.627	1.412	1.001	1.382
	$\kappa_s \times 10^{10} \text{ (Pa}^{-1}\text{)}$					
0.00	5.015	8.164	5.469	5.01	8.16	5.47
0.25	4.953	8.024	5.039	4.92	8.09	5.43
0.50	4.926	7.885	4.339	4.83	7.99	5.42
0.75	4.888	7.734	4.059	4.75	7.93	5.34
1.00	4.862	7.610	3.826	4.71	7.84	5.32
	$b \times 10^5 \text{ (m}^3\text{)}$					
0.00	7.748	9.157	8.603	7.747	9.157	8.603
0.25	7.845	9.346	8.723	7.837	9.346	8.673
0.50	7.987	9.480	8.839	7.980	9.479	8.783
0.75	8.126	9.556	8.952	8.120	9.677	8.897
1.00	8.273	9.655	9.060	8.261	9.871	9.006
	$L_r \times 10^{11} \text{ (m)}$					
0.00	4.69	5.98	4.90	4.69	5.98	4.90
0.25	4.66	5.93	4.70	4.64	5.96	4.88
0.50	4.65	5.88	4.36	4.60	5.92	4.87
0.75	4.63	5.82	4.22	4.56	5.90	4.84
1.00	4.62	5.78	4.10	4.54	5.86	4.83
	$\pi \times 10^{-8} \text{ (Pa)}$					
0.00	4.763	3.257	4.826	4.763	3.257	4.826
0.25	4.544	3.221	4.923	4.775	3.140	5.105
0.50	4.464	3.195	4.718	4.721	3.126	5.107
0.75	4.380	3.175	4.623	4.632	3.063	5.025
1.00	4.363	3.170	4.521	4.548	3.023	4.976
	$V_r \times 10^7 \text{ (m}^3\text{)}$					
0.00	–	–	–	–	–	–
0.25	2.148	4.235	1.367	1.854	4.571	1.240
0.50	2.187	4.218	1.516	1.852	4.506	1.207
0.75	2.237	4.233	1.573	1.895	4.598	1.236
1.00	2.183	4.166	1.642	1.935	4.598	1.242
	S_n					
0.00	–	–	–	–	–	–
0.25	2.20	1.92	0.26	1.44	3.64	3.02
0.50	3.06	1.93	0.21	1.50	3.17	4.67
0.75	4.62	2.88	0.30	2.27	4.79	7.05
1.00	4.33	2.48	0.33	2.09	4.68	3.49

Table 3. Least square equations and correlation coefficients for BPDA and DHDEBP at 30 °C

Parameter	DO	BPDA	DMF	MEK
	ρ (kg/m ³)	1.881C + 1007.1 $R^2 = 0.992$		1.541C + 934.7 $R^2 = 0.999$
η (m.Pas)	0.0316C + 1.082 $R^2 = 0.991$		0.018C + 0.696 $R^2 = 0.844$	0.017C + 0.376 $R^2 = 0.992$
U (m s ⁻¹)	98.133C + 1354.8 $R^2 = 0.951$		5.8667C + 1465.4 $R^2 = 0.995$	6.2222C + 1263.6 $R^2 = 0.987$
$Z \times 10^{-5}$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	0.102C + 1.364 $R^2 = 0.955$		0.007C + 1.369 $R^2 = 0.993$	0.022C + 0.968 $R^2 = 0.998$
$\kappa_s \times 10^{10}$ (Pas)	-0.581C + 5.296 $R^2 = 0.926$		-0.046C + 4.985 $R^2 = 0.994$	-0.206C + 8.162 $R^2 = 0.999$
$R \times 10^4$ (m ^{10/3} s ^{-1/3} mol ⁻¹)	0.409C + 9.669 $R^2 = 0.984$		0.254C + 8.876 $R^2 = 0.999$	0.178C + 10.172 $R^2 = 0.987$
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	-0.193C + 5.022 $R^2 = 0.962$		-0.093C + 4.594 $R^2 = 0.939$	-0.026C + 3.234 $R^2 = 0.928$
L_f	-0.309C + 4.871 $R^2 = 0.967$		-0.026C + 4.683 $R^2 = 0.974$	-0.078C + 5.983 $R^2 = 0.999$
V_f	0.131C + 1.392 $R^2 = 0.949$		0.023C + 2.166 $R^2 = 0.303$	-0.029C + 4.242 $R^2 = 0.595$
		DHDEBP		
ρ (kg/m ³)	1.2C + 1012.9 $R^2 = 0.9918$		1.541C + 934.75 $R^2 = 0.9996$	4.504C + 774.65 $R^2 = 0.8455$
η (m.Pas)	0.026C + 1.120 $R^2 = 0.8769$		0.019C + 0.78 $R^2 = 0.9211$	0.013C + 0.359 $R^2 = 0.9724$
U (m s ⁻¹)	7.170C + 1341.6 $R^2 = 0.8855$		15.467C + 1464.4 $R^2 = 0.9814$	5.926C + 126 $R^2 = 0.9524$
$Z \times 10^{-5}$ (kg m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	0.009C + 1.359 $R^2 = 0.9276$		0.017C + 1.369 $R^2 = 0.986$	0.010C + 0.974 $R^2 = 0.9776$
$\kappa_s \times 10^{10}$ (Pas)	-0.063C + 5.484 $R^2 = 0.9093$		-0.108C + 4.985 $R^2 = 0.9819$	-0.120C + 8.167 $R^2 = 0.9945$
$R \times 10^4$ (m ^{10/3} s ^{-1/3} mol ⁻¹)	0.201C + 9.580 $R^2 = 0.9987$		0.272C + 8.867 $R^2 = 0.9997$	0.303C + 10.035 $R^2 = 0.9913$
$\pi \times 10^{-8}$ (Pa)	-0.069C + 5.171 $R^2 = 0.8899$		-0.115C + 4.862 $R^2 = 0.9897$	-0.062C + 3.192 $R^2 = 0.953$
L_f	-0.016C + 4.901 $R^2 = 0.842$		-0.033C + 4.686 $R^2 = 0.830$	-0.027C + 5.988 $R^2 = 0.912$
V_f	0.005C + 1.222 $R^2 = 0.0814$		0.042C + 1.813 $R^2 = 0.875$	0.025C + 4.526 $R^2 = 0.263$

acoustical impedance (Z), isentropic compressibility (κ_s), Van der Waals constant (b), inter molecular free path length (L_f), internal pressure (π), free volume (V_f) and solvation number (S_n) were derived according to following standard equations :

Acoustical impedance, $Z = U\rho$

Isentropic compressibility, $\kappa_s = \frac{1}{U^2\rho}$

Van der Waals constant,

$$b = \frac{M}{\rho} \left[1 - \left[\frac{RT}{MU^2} \right] \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{MU^2}{3RT}} - 1 \right] \right]$$

Inter molecular path length, $L_f = K.(\kappa_s)^{1/2}$

Internal pressure, $\pi = bRT \left(\frac{K\eta}{U} \right)^{1/2} \frac{\rho^{2/3}}{M^{1/6}}$

$$\text{Free volume, } V_f = \left[\frac{MU}{K\eta} \right]^{3/2}$$

$$\text{Solvation number, } S_n = \frac{M_2}{M_1 \left(1 - \frac{\kappa_s}{\kappa_{sl}} \right) \left(\frac{100 - X}{X} \right)}$$

The ρ , η and U increased linearly with C in all the three solvent systems studied. Above mentioned parameters were correlated with concentration (C). The least square equations along with regression coefficients (R^2) are reported in Table 3.

From Table 1, it is observed that ρ is increased little with C , but η and U increased considerably with C . The linear increase of ρ , η and U with C confirmed solvent-solute interactions in the solutions.

The change in U and ρ with C is not as appreciable as η because molecular motion is much more affected by solvent-solute interactions¹.

Z , b and V_f increased linearly with C , while κ_s , L_f and π decreased linearly with C . Linear increase or decrease of the said parameters suggested the presence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions. A fairly good to excellent correlation between a specified parameter and C is observed (Table 2).

Increase of ρ , η and U with C supports the increase of cohesive forces due to powerful molecular interactions^{8,9}. The density and viscosity of the medium, pressure, temperature, etc. affect the velocity. Depending on the nature of the solvent and solute, molecular interactions may either lead to contraction or expansion. Internal pressure of a solution is sensitive to molecular interactions namely solute-solvent interactions, quantum mechanical dispersion forces and dielectric forces, which play an important role in transport properties of the solutions. Decrease of π and increase of V_f and L_f with C suggested decrease of cohesive forces. Decrease of κ_s with C supported fully compressed solvated molecules by electrical forces present in the solute molecules due to strong solute-solvent interactions. Thus, studied acoustical parameters suggested solvophilic nature of BPDA and DHDEBP and it is further confirmed by positive values of S_n (Fig. 1). From Fig. 1, it is clear that S_n increased

up to about 2 mol L⁻¹ and then decreased with C for both compounds in the studied systems. The observed trend in S_n for the compounds is DO > MEK > DMF for DHDEBP and DMF > MEK > DO for BPDA.

The decrease of S_n with C confirmed powerful solute-solute interactions over solvent-solute interactions¹⁰. Molecular interactions depend upon the nature and structure of the solvents and the solutes, temperature, pressure, nature of the substituent, etc. The presence of polar substituents in the solute molecules will enhance molecular interactions. Solvation causes change in apparent molar volume and hence compressibility of the molecules. Thus, S_n is a measure of the structure forming or breaking tendency of solutes. DHDEBP has comparatively more structure forming tendency than BPDA due to -COCH₃ and -OH groups. The dipole-dipole interactions of opposite type favor structure formation, while of the same type favor disruption of structure formed previously. The lone pairs of electrons of -COCH₃, -OCOCH₃, -OH, DO, MEK and DMF are electronegative groups, while -CH₃ and -OH hydrogens are electropositive groups. Due to powerful H-bond formation between -COCH₃ and -OH of DHDEBP and oxygen of L O, a large positive value of S_n is observed.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, derived acoustical parameters suggested the presence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions. Both the compounds possess structure forming tendency in solvent systems studied.

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Madhvi *et al.* : Ultrasonic velocity and molecular interaction study of biphenol derivatives at 30° C

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